

GUIDELINES FOR THE DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SCENARIOS IN WILIAM

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. MOTIVATION	2
2. OBJECTIVE OF THE DOCUMENT	2
3. GLOSSARY	3
4. WILIAM OVERVIEW	14
4.1. SHORT DESCRIPTION	14
4.2. DOCUMENTATION AND MATERIALS	16
5. SCENARIO METHODOLOGY APPLIED TO WILIAM	16
5.1. GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS	16
5.2. WORKFLOW	17
5.2.1. <i>DEFINITION OF THE STORYLINE AND THE WILIAM EXOGENOUS VARIABLES</i>	19
5.2.2. <i>DEFINING THE STORYLINES</i>	19
5.2.2.1. <i>STORYLINE GOALS</i>	20
5.2.2.2. <i>QUALITATIVE ATTRIBUTE TABLES</i>	20
5.2.3. <i>PARAMETRIZATION OF SCENARIOS</i>	24
6. SOME IDEAS FOR HELPING TO INTERPRET WILIAM RESULTS	28
7. IDEAS TO LINK WILIAM WITH A LOCAL MODEL	30
8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	31
9. BIBLIOGRAPHY	31
10. APPENDIX I	35
1. GUIDELINES FOR THE DOCUMENTATION OF THE PARAMETRIZATION PROCESS OF A SCENARIO IN WILIAM	35
1.1. <i>GENERAL WORKFLOW</i>	35
1.1.1. <i>MAINTENANCE AND UPDATING OF SCENARIO INPUT EXCELS</i>	38

1. MOTIVATION

The WILIAM model has hundreds of policies and hypotheses distributed across all the modules (economy, land-use, energy, etc.). IAMs, in general, have such an amount of complexity that a clear methodology is needed to deal with it. In this case, we chose the Scenario Methodology to show results from the WILIAM model in a coordinated and structured way. This is also necessary for dissemination and communication purposes, as we need to focus on a limited and as relevant as possible set of results.

Scenarios are plausible descriptions of how the future might evolve (Moss et al., 2010; Shukla et al., 2022) and can be of qualitative and/or quantitative character. The qualitative part of a scenario might also be referred to as 'storyline' or 'narrative', which might be combined with a quantitative part (e.g. simulations through quantitative models). The selection of a limited set of scenarios means that these will be coarse: we trade-off precision for feasibility of the analysis -and we must live with it, since we need to produce results for dissemination. These results have to represent a balance between accuracy and those messages we convey.

Through Scenario Methodology, we project different alternatives, always keeping in mind that the objective is to do a comparative analysis between these alternatives and not to forecast. In order to implement scenarios in IAMs, we need a series of elements that will allow us to run simulations. These elements are mainly policies and hypotheses, which are introduced to the model as exogenous inputs. In IAMs, policies are often modelled as policy targets, that is, modelled as the intended effect of a given policy measure or a combination of policies (for example, by setting a target for the maximum amount of CO₂ emitted per year). IAMs focus on interrelations between dimensions and do not go to the detail of each of them, since they research general strategies to move towards sustainability. Hypotheses, on the other hand, in the scope of WILIAM, are understood as parameters which have to be defined, but they are not controllable by humans. They are the same for all sets of baseline and policy-action scenarios to ensure comparability.

All these reasons have given rise to the creation of this guideline. The next pages include a glossary with agreed definitions of the main concepts used in the scenario literature, which shall establish a common conceptual framework. Also, a methodology to create global, regional and national scenarios, as well as to implement them in WILIAM, will be explained. To complement this document, researchers can also check the [WILIAM 1.3 User Guide](#) for technical issues when running the model.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE DOCUMENT

The main objective of this document is to create a common guideline and framework describing how to design a scenario and implement it in WILIAM¹. It is important to highlight that the aim of this guide is not to show how to model new policies, but to create scenarios with the ones that are already modelled and can be used through `scenario_parameters.xlsx`. If the user wants to model new policies, please contact the WILIAM Scenarios Coordinator (raquel.gallego@uva.es).

In summary, this document aims at enhancing the autonomy of the WILIAM users. We would like to highlight that it is a living document which will be completed and improved with its use, so feedback to the authors is encouraged!

¹ Structure refers to the equations and logical relationships between exogenous and endogenous parameters to reproduce a given policy/hypothesis consistent with a storyline, while parametrization means the quantification of exogenous parameters to reproduce a given policy/hypothesis consistent with a given storyline.

3. GLOSSARY

The glossary includes a general definition of the term scenario, as well as practical examples and specificities, if there are any, in the use of each term in the WILIAM model. The objective is to share a common terminology to be used in the context of WILIAM. The definitions will be based as much as possible on the common use of the terms in literature and general use of language, taking into account that there may be different uses of the terms across different disciplines.

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
Storyline or narrative	<p>An a priori consistent story or narrative of how the future may evolve. Storylines define the core of each scenario, describing its main characteristics, drivers and dynamics. They are qualitative descriptions of the trajectories of the economic, social, technological, environmental, and political evolution that the world may follow in the near future². They also provide information on relationships and feedback loops between key drivers; hence, it implicitly includes a certain number of policy objectives and targets.</p> <p>The most common narratives in the climate science literature are the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). They represent a relevant set of storylines since they are standard in the climate science community (this does not mean that we cannot simulate other storylines which are not considered within the SSPs).</p>	<p>Since the WILIAM model is divided into 9 different world regions (some modules have a disaggregation of 35 regions= 8 + the European Union disaggregated in its 27 countries), we can consider different storylines for different regions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Business As Usual ▪ Fossil-fuelled Development ▪ Inequality ▪ Green Growth ▪ Regional Rivalry ▪ Post Growth 	<p>(O'Neill et al., 2017; Ribeiro et al., 2022; Shukla et al., 2022)</p>

² In the case of WILIAM, we consider 2050 the “near future”, as it is the year in which the results of the model are reliable.

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
Hypotheses	<p>Assumptions made in the model which serve as exogenous inputs, and which are subject to uncertainty. They typically refer to biophysical realities that are not controllable by human societies.</p> <p>Another way of defining hypotheses in WILIAM is that they are assumptions, represented as quantitative scenario parameters (subject to uncertainty), that do not usually depend on political actions.</p> <p>The key issue regarding hypotheses is that they are a range of estimations and, depending on the use of these estimations, scenario results change. Changes in hypothesis generates different baseline scenarios, not policy-action scenarios. They can also be used to explore uncertainty scenarios.</p>	<p>In the WILIAM framework, hypotheses can be changed to build different baseline scenarios. Others remain fix and are considered model parameters that do not change by any type of scenario.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Oil reserves ▪ Mineral reserves ▪ Tipping points ▪ “How much oil is available at X extraction cost in region Z?” 	N/A
Scenario	<p>Scenarios are plausible descriptions of how the future might evolve and can be of qualitative and/or quantitative character. The qualitative part of a scenario might also be referred to as 'storyline' or 'narrative', which might be combined with a quantitative part (e.g.</p>	<p>As it happens with the storylines, we can simulate combined scenarios by selecting different scenarios for the different regions.</p>	<p>Same names as for storylines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Business As Usual ▪ Fossil-fuelled Development ▪ Inequality ▪ Green Growth ▪ Regional Rivalry 	(Moss et al., 2010; Shukla et al., 2022)

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	<p>simulations through quantitative models).</p> <p>Scenarios can inform and guide decision-makers by creating normative, descriptive, or exploratory alternatives, expanding cognitive limitations from bounded realities and formulating relatable and plausible future narratives.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post Growth 	
Baseline or reference scenario	<p>A baseline scenario is an explorative scenario in which most of the exogenous model parameters are hypotheses calibrated to represent a concrete pathway, typically being current/historical trends, but it does not explicitly include policy measures. These kinds of scenarios refer to IAMs employed in their “free-running” state. Normally, the reference scenario reproduces issues (e.g., the impossibility to reach certain objectives such as staying below 1.5°C average global temperature increase) that prompt us to simulate alternative futures by introducing specific policies.</p> <p>Baseline scenarios are often also called Reference, No policy or Business As</p>	N/A	(European Commission. Directorate General for Energy. et al., 2021)	(Markovska et al., 2023; Pielke & Ritchie, 2021)

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	Usual (BAU) scenarios. They allow researchers to clearly identify -in the modelling results- the separate influence of the introduced policies by measuring changes in results from the baseline.			
Adaptative scenario	<p>The trajectory of the initially defined scenario can be modified due to the internal constraints present in the model or endogenous dynamics of the model. Thus, an adaptative scenario is a scenario which does not attain its predefined goals.</p> <p>It is the final and more complete 'scenario output', consistently viable with the structural and parametric conditions of the model ("realistic"). These scenarios vary depending on the model used to obtain the results.</p>	Most of the core variables that would be basic to define scenario (e.g. the GHG emissions) are endogenous in WILIAM, so its final set of the scenarios will be not only defined by the predefined inputs, but also by the model results.	Same names as for storylines	
Policy-action scenario	These scenarios are applied on top of baseline scenarios, so that every scenario starts as a baseline and gradually becomes a policy-action one. It includes a series of policy measures which are simulated to gauge their effectiveness in reaching the goals of the storylines.	N/A	Same names as for storylines	https://archive.ipcc.ch/ipccreports/tar/wg2/index.php?idp=126 (Pielke & Ritchie, 2021)

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	Policy-action scenarios are also called normative scenarios.			
Explorative scenario	<p>Explorative scenarios refer to those exploring possible futures focusing on different hypotheses, whereas normative scenarios usually compare a central projection with variants that involve policy interventions.</p> <p>Typically, the central projection is called the baseline or reference.</p>			(Van Vuuren et al., 2012)
Back-casting scenario	<p>Scenario technique that consists of defining a desirable future characterised by some endpoints and goes back to the reasons and actions that connect the present with those points. In target oriented backcasting scenarios, the pathways do not lead up to the scenarios, but it is the other way round.</p> <p>The back-casting approach is used to create scenarios can be applied to see what would need to happen and which actions would be needed to be taken to reach the preferred future. It is often combined with the policy-scenario approach (see above).</p>	N/A	N/A	(Bibri, 2018; Evans Pim & Dom, 2021; Svenfelt et al., 2019)

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
Forecast scenario	Scenarios based on a set of imposed rules defined from the base year onwards. This approach is often combined with the explorative scenario approach.	N/A	N/A	N/A
Policy	<p>A set of ideas or a plan of what to do in particular situations that has been agreed by a group of targeted people, business organisation, government or political party.</p> <p>Different types of policies can be defined depending on their scope, and they mustn't be confounded with policy measures which are more specific.</p>	<p>In the WILIAM framework, they consist of interventions typically promoted by institutions such as government and regulatory institutions.</p> <p>As the concept is very general, it is preferable to work with policy objectives, policy targets and policy measures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy Policy ▪ Trade Policy ▪ Labour Policy ▪ Health Policy ▪ Environmental Policy 	<p>https://dictionary.cambridge.org/es-LA/dictionary/english/policy</p>
Storyline/scenario policy goal	<p>Broad, general policy objective at societal level which are the basis for developing policy recommendations.</p> <p>We further distinguish between goals identified as drivers of a given storyline (storyline drivers), and those which the model users may want to check if a given storyline is able to fulfil (other goals).</p> <p>Considering a "Green Growth" storyline, an example of a storyline goal is</p>	<p>So far, WILIAM goals have been selected from the following sources and complemented with additional goals as climate change tipping points (Lenton et al., 2008), planetary boundaries (Steffen et al., 2015), UNFCCC Paris Agreement,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Full net decarbonisation by 2050 ▪ Achieve full employment ▪ Maintain a certain level of societal equity ▪ Transition to 100% renewables 	N/A

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	<p>“absolute decoupling of environmental pressures from economic growth”. An example of other goals under a Green Growth story is “Preserving or improving life expectancy” or “Gender equality/Non-discrimination of women and girls”. Both types of goals act as “benchmarks” to gauge whether a simulated scenario leads to a desirable solution to the identified problems. They are also indicators that allow us to evaluate the feasibility of the storylines. Therefore, they require measurable variables that can be used as indicators to verify the fulfilment of these goals. Indicators can be compared against a threshold or a target.</p>	<p>UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Annual GDPpc growth of 3% ▪ SDGs, etc. 	
Scenario drivers	<p>Drivers can be understood as trends that play a critical role in the future development of critical model variables and results, such as population size and economic development. For several of these, exogenous assumptions are made and they push forward the outcome of model calculations, together with the endogenous functional relationships</p>	<p>In WILIAM, storylines are guided by certain logics and motivations. Therefore, goals can act as drivers for the storylines.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Population development ▪ Productivities improvement (labour, capital, etc.) 	<p>https://models.pbl.nl/image/index.php/Drivers (Crespo et al., 2020)</p>

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	and model parameters in the model. Also, the assumptions for the drivers are based on scenario narratives or storylines.			
Policy objective	<p>It refers to the generally formulated desired outcome of a policy. It should not be confused with policy target (see below), which refers to a specific quantified level or rate set for the chosen objective.</p> <p>These are tried to be achieved by means of modelling concrete policy measures, which may cater to more than one policy objective.</p>	<p>WILIAM is designed to model policy measures rather than policy objectives or targets. However, in some modules of WILIAM, there is not enough detail to introduce policy measures. In these specific cases, we will introduce policy targets.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Decarbonization ▪ Transition to renewables ▪ Reduce unemployment ▪ Reduce inequalities ▪ GDPpc growth ▪ Increase exports ▪ Decrease energy use in buildings 	N/A
Policy target	<p>Quantifiable intended effect (or expected outcome) of a policy measure. Also defined as the operationalization or quantification of the policy objective, although a policy target can be linked to more than one policy objective³.</p> <p>In IAMs, most policies are typically modelled as policy targets. They focus on interrelations between dimensions and does not go to the detail of each of</p>	<p>When we introduce a policy measure in WILIAM, policy target is used to assess whether the policy measure meets its closest or direct aim. When this is not possible and we have to directly introduce the policy target in WILIAM, it is used to represent a policy itself and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 32% of renewable energy in total energy by 2030 ▪ Increasing public transport passengers by 20% ▪ Reducing the same 20% of private transport passengers 	

³ It is important to highlight that there exists a hierarchical many-to-many relationship between most of the concepts. In this case, a policy objective can be linked to many policy targets. The same happens with policy goals, that can be linked to many policy objectives, and with policy targets that can be linked to many policy measures.

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	them, which is necessary to model policy measures. IAMs research sustainability general strategies.	analyse the resulting consequences in the whole model ⁴ .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reducing meat consumption in the diet by 10% ▪ Targets from the SDGs 	
Policy instrument	Mechanisms and tools to implement policy measures and eventually reach policy targets. It should also be considered that a same policy instrument may contribute to implement different policy measures and reach different targets.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Laws ▪ Regulations ▪ Codes ▪ Subsidies ▪ Taxes ▪ Campaigns to raise awareness ▪ New infrastructure projects for transport or urban planning ▪ Focused education and training for professionals ▪ Obligation schemes ▪ Public procurement 	(Böck et al., 2020)
Policy measure	A specific intervention in different parts of the system, and which can be specified through quantifiable targets (policy targets) and is implemented	This is the smallest unit of the policy analysis in the WILIAM scenario framework.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carbon tax ▪ Raising awareness ▪ Subsidies to specific technologies or R&D 	

⁴ This method is only used when we cannot model policy measures due to lack of detail. If we introduce policy targets instead, it is important to highlight it because we are making strong assumptions, and many important causal chains and realism will be lost (e.g., if we introduce a 100% recycling rate, we are assuming that this is possible and we can analyse effects of that policy targets in other parts of WILIAM, although this is a very likely non-feasible target to reach due to technical, political and social constraints).

	Definition	WILIAM specificities	Examples	References
	<p>through policy instruments such as financial aids, benefits, taxes, information campaigns, training, etc.</p> <p>The interventions are typically promoted by institutions such as governments and regulatory institutions to drive a technological, behavioural, infrastructure, etc. change with relation to current trends.</p> <p>Note that the same policy measure may contribute to reaching multiple targets.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New laws limiting or prohibiting the consumption or production of polluting products 	

4. WILIAM OVERVIEW

4.1. SHORT DESCRIPTION

The Within Limits Integrated Assessment Model (WILIAM) is a system dynamics policy-simulation model, descendent from the MEDEAS model (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2020), which has been designed to explore long-term decarbonization pathways within planetary boundaries by addressing a series of limitations of existing IAMs. In fact, despite the high number of IAMs, many of them share several relevant and disputable hypotheses/characteristics. The main shortcomings aimed to be addressed with WILIAM are:

- Lack of plurality/simplified representation of economic processes typically based on optimization.
- Equilibrium dynamics.
- Aggregate production functions and representative agents (Hardt & O’Neill, 2017; Scricciu et al., 2013).
- Future energy transitions modelled as demand-driven transformations (assumption of future high energy availability at affordable cost, both for renewables and non-renewables).
- The neglect of implications of future energy investments required to achieve the transition to renewables for the entire system Energy Return on Energy Investment of the full system (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2019).
- Difficulties to reach 100% renewable systems.
- Underestimation of the damages caused by climate change.
- The absence of the material dimension and key sustainability dimensions other than climate change.

WILIAM focuses on the detailed representation of the economic processes following a Dynamic Econometric Input-Output approach and consistently linking the economic and biophysical spheres according to the principles of Ecological Macroeconomics. WILIAM follows a complex system approach, in which the interactions between dimensions are more relevant than the complexity within each module. System

Figure 1. WILIAM (v1.1) simplified structure overview. Main linkages between modules.

Dynamics allows to capture complex feedback loops and nonlinear relationships among social, economic, and environmental variables.

WILIAM comprises 8 modules of Earth and human systems: (1) Demography, (2) Society, (3) Economy, (4) Finance, (5) Energy, (6) Materials, (7) Land and Water, and (8) Climate. Figure 1 shows the structure overview with the main linkages between modules. Different modules reach different levels of detail and complexity. WILIAM starts to run in 2005 and typically runs until 2060, although the simulation horizon may be extended to 2100. WILIAM is a multiregional model which blends top-down and bottom-up (end-use) modelling approaches, and it integrates knowledge and methods from different disciplines aiming to capture the main dynamics between human and natural systems. This comprehensive integration is particularly relevant when modelling disruptive scenarios involving significant shifts in economic structure, social values, norms, and individual behaviour. Indeed, the ultimate goal of WILIAM is to explore the social, economic, and environmental implications at the global and regional levels of long-term socio-ecological transition pathways, considering biophysical planetary limits as well as socio-economic constraints. The validation of the model has been carried out following several of the usual validation procedures of models in system dynamics (Barlas, 1996; Sterman, 2000). The historical data has been used for a first validation, and the results will also be compared with other models.

Below is a summary of the main characteristics of WILIAM model:

- Open source (MIT license).
- Modular structure.
- Detailed geographical coverage: multi-regional world model with 8 global regions and the integration of the 27 EU countries individually for some dimensions.
- Modules for demography and society, which allow to consider feedbacks such as migration and the effects of climate change on population.
- The economy is represented by a dynamic econometric model covering 35 regions, with detailed representation of consumption (including 60 household's types), production (based on input-output tables of 62 sectors), government (including collection of taxes + public expenditures), investment, labour, international trade and financial dimensions.
- Transport: a detailed representation of passenger transport including 11 transport modes, 10 power trains and a portfolio of behavioural policies.
- Energy supply: representation with high detail of the full energy supply-chain through the main refinery, transformation, and supply processes.
- Variability of renewables keeps track of sub-annual time scale effects on annual energy balances depending on the current power system setup of build-up of generation capacities and flexibility capacities (demand-side management, storage, sector coupling, hydrogen and synthetic fuels).
- Computation of the EROI of the full system considering the EROI and material requirements of green technologies, which feedbacks the energy demand.
- Techno-sustainable potentials of renewables considering biophysical, geographical, natural resources and EROI constraints.
- Modules of fossil fuels and metals fully integrated with Energy and Economy modules. The models are driven by a demand-price mechanism in which a higher price 1) reduces the demand for materials,

and 2) triggers investment to increase the material extraction capacity, limited by available resources and increasing depletion rates.

- Land-use module including human food, energy, and climate interactions, thus allowing endogenizing land-based renewable potentials (solar and bioenergy), considering the agriculture and land related emissions, and the effects of climate change on biophysical variables such as crop yields.
- Water module: main outputs are water availability and water stress based on demand and supply.
- Climate module converting emissions coming from the other modules in changes in main climate variables, such as mean temperature change and sea level rise.
- Climate change impacts on capital stock and labour productivity.
- The improvement in scenario assessment by integrating demand management policies across modules, particularly for passenger transport and diets.
- A rich portfolio of conventional and heterodox policies (CO₂ taxes, basic income, behavioural changes, working time reduction, recycling, etc.) aiming at being able to simulate a broad range of narratives, such as Green Growth, Green Deal and Post-growth/Degrowth.

Overall, the result is a new IAM, which in combination with a pluralistic view to assess future policy-action storylines, will very likely offer alternative insights on future transitions.

4.2. DOCUMENTATION AND MATERIALS

For detailed information about the WILIAM structure and modules, different documents and materials are available:

- LOCOMOTION D9.3 (August 2023) report includes the links and feedbacks between them and the validation process, as well as the preliminary results of the model. Check (Lifi et al., 2023).
- LOCOMOTION D11.2 (August 2023) e-Handbook. To have a deeper understanding of the WILIAM model main purpose and the conceptual models and hypothesis included in each of its module, check the WILIAM e-handbook present in (Samsó et al., 2023).
- WILIAM MOOC: <https://www.locomotion-h2020.eu/locomotion-massive-open-on-line-course-moc/>
- GitHub repository: updated documentation regarding WILIAM will be uploaded online [here](#).

5. SCENARIO METHODOLOGY APPLIED TO WILIAM

5.1. GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Performing simulations with models can be a cumbersome task when the models have many parameters and hypotheses of uncertain evolution, as well as an almost infinite possible combinations of policy measures which can be varied at the same time. The scenario methodology offers an approach to deal with the limited knowledge, uncertainty and complexity of natural and social sciences and, when applied to this kind of models, it can be used to group the different future possibilities into coherent and meaningful scenarios.

Each scenario is based on a storyline which represents a (qualitative) archetypical and coherent vision of the future, which may be viewed positively by some people and negatively by others. Each of these storylines already include implicitly some hypotheses and policies (e.g., the BAU scenario from the World Energy Outlook from the IEA is typically termed “Current Policies”). Moreover, each of these storylines are driven by certain

logics and motivations, which we have termed here “goals driving the storyline”. A classic example within IAMs would be the pursuit of 2-3%/year GDPpc growth with regional convergence.

In a second step, policy scenarios are designed on top of the baseline scenarios in order to add or enhance policy targets and measures that will lead to reach a pre-defined expanded set of goals beyond those driving the storyline. In climate IAMs, a classical pre-defined overall goal is the staying below 2°C by 2100. This scenario methodology has been widely used in Global Environmental Assessments such as the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, the UNEP’s Global Environmental Outlook or the successive IPCC reports -SRES, SSPs- (e.g., (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (Program), 2005); (Riahi et al., 2017); (*SSP Database*, 2018); (Van Vuuren et al., 2012)).

However, we should also consider that, within these institutional frameworks, national governments have a say (e.g., veto right in the case of the IPCC) and the scenarios issued from these institutional processes cannot hence be considered as unbiased “purely” scientific outcomes (e.g., (Girod et al., 2009)). Hence, this should also be taken into account when applying existing scenarios or developing new ones to be simulated in WILIAM.

Moreover, WILIAM has a very specific and particular structure and approach, so it may not be fully equipped to simulate certain sets of scenarios due to, for example, the dimensions represented in WILIAM which are not represented in other IAMs (e.g., mineral requirements) or variables which are exogenous in other IAMs which are endogenous in WILIAM (e.g. GDP, which in WILIAM is a model output). Hence, the current IPCC scheme (RCPs-SSPs-SPAs) is not totally suitable for WILIAM, since:

- In WILIAM (as in MEDEAS):
 - GDPpc is endogenous (population is also planned to be endogenous in the close future)
 - Includes goals beyond climate change targets
- SSPs exclude:
 - Climate change impacts
 - Postgrowth scenarios (Hickel et al., 2021)

It is key to understand that the power of IAMs does not lie in prediction, but in the intercomparison of applying different policies in different plausible contexts and assess which ones would be the most beneficial in a succession of “what-if” exercises. MEDEAS and WILIAM models work under the logic of “adaptive scenarios”: at the beginning of the simulation there are some current trends + policies that are expected to happen within a given general context (storyline), but then feedbacks may or may not allow these current trends and policies to really happen in the future. In this sense, MEDEAS/WILIAM models especially focus on biophysical (e.g., land, water, mineral and energy availability) and socioeconomic constraints (e.g., economic structure, available income) (for more information on this go to (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2020)).

Of course, it is neither possible to develop a model with full predictive power, nor do we intend to achieve that. And also in the real world, if the narrative happens to be unfeasible in a given point in the future, there will be changes in the socio-cultural dimension (which our model is not intended to capture) which will deviate the storyline from the one initially set. However, this kind of changes are beyond the scope of IAM modelling and belong to the discussion about the limits of modelling for policy advice.

5.2. WORKFLOW

Now, to build a scenario that will be implemented in WILIAM, it is necessary to follow a series of steps, which are synthesised in Figure 2:

Figure 2. Workflow of the elaboration of scenarios in WILIAM.

- Qualitatively define the storylines and identify the exogenous variables of the model, which will be those that will be used for implementing scenarios. The most practical thing to do is conduct these two tasks in parallel when using WILIAM, since storyline definition is to a certain extent conditioned by the model structure, even though that the model can also be subject to changes in the structure to introduce variables that are needed for implementing a scenario.
- Conduct the ‘qualification of storylines’, which refers to assigning qualitative dimensions to the storylines; these will serve afterwards to guide future scenario quantification. For this step we use tools such as the goals and qualitative attribute tables.
- Third, we link those pre-defined qualitative attributes to specific targets and measures, and we set quantitative targets and thresholds. This is how we go from a storyline to a scenario.

It is important to remember that for each scenario, it should be justified which parameters are used for each policy and hypothesis. In order to have traceability of the process to create a scenario, we have created an .xlsx file where everything, from the storyline to the parametrization, can be documented. This documentation material can be found in Appendix I.

In addition, Figure 3 represent the different steps required to simulate a scenario with WILIAM. Regarding simulation, the efficacy of each scenario will be assessed by comparing the obtained value of the model outputs to the pre-defined set of goals. These goals may or may not be achieved. Since WILIAM includes a number of feedbacks representing physical and social constraints, the exact behaviour of the model is not easily predictable, and it may happen that some storylines are ultimately not feasible. This is not in contradiction with the whole framework given that the result are “adaptive scenarios”.

Figure 3. Conceptual representation of the steps required to simulate a scenario with the WILIAM model. Source: Iñigo Capellán-Pérez (own work).

5.2.1. DEFINITION OF THE STORYLINE AND THE WILIAM EXOGENOUS VARIABLES

Having said this, now it is time to start shaping the scenarios in order to simulate and analyse them. For this step it is important to have understood the concepts defined in the glossary, as well as to take into account the differences between exploratory and normative scenarios. In explorative or baseline scenarios, there are not explicitly implemented policies, whereas in normative or policy action scenarios, there are. Therefore, the main aspects to have in mind are:

- Variations in hypotheses will lead to new baseline scenarios.
- Application and variation of policy measures and targets will lead to new policy-action scenarios.
- Policy-action scenarios are applied on top of baseline scenarios, so that every scenario starts as a baseline and gradually changes.

Differentiating between hypotheses and other scenario parameters, such as policy or behavioural change measures and targets, is key to guarantee the coherence and transparency in scenario building. In this manner, we can attribute results across scenarios to specific assumptions.

Finally, we should be reminded that all the steps that compound the process of building and running scenarios in WILIAM can be used in the same way for global, regional/EU and national scenarios. As explained above, WILIAM is a global multiregional model in which the world is disaggregated into 9 (or 35, depending on the module/variable) regions. This means that we can make a wide variety of regionalized scenarios.

5.2.2. DEFINING THE STORYLINES

The first thing to do is defining a storyline about how the future world might unfold (including potential regional heterogeneities). The importance of a well-written storyline lies on the fact that they can be an understandable way of communicating information about the future (Alcamo, 2008). A storyline must include

qualitative information for each storyline on the main underlying hypotheses, the implicit policy targets and measures, as well as the identification of the drivers of the storyline which will be pursued by the model.

5.2.2.1. STORYLINE GOALS

The storyline goals are used to determine exogenous inputs to the model to ensure that the storyline is properly translated into a scenario. These goals can be also interpreted as drivers for a given storyline and they refer to those elements which the model users may want to check if a given storyline are able to fulfil. An example of a storyline goal is “(absolute) decoupling of environmental pressures from economic growth” in the Green Growth storyline and scenario. Table 1 shows an example of environmental and socio-economic goals in Green Growth, Green Deal and Post-Growth storylines. In this case, it can be observed some of the main differences between them; while Green Growth and Green Deal have a GDPpc growth as an economic goal, Post-growth is driven by the idea of economic re-localization. Environmental goals, on the other hand, are prioritized in all storylines, albeit through different meanings. Finally, Green Growth does not have a socio-economic goal, while Green Deal and Post-growth have specific inclusion policies.

Table 1. Example of storyline goals in three proposed storylines (Green Growth, Green Deal and Post-Growth). Source: (Samsó et al., 2023)

Goals	Green Growth	Green Deal	Post-growth
Environmental	Prioritized, through markets and innovation	Prioritized, through markets and innovation, regulation and large public expenditures	Prioritized, through transformation of economy, regulation, production slowdown and behavioural change
Economic	Sustained economic growth	Sustained economic growth	Steady-state economy or degrowth (economic contraction)
Social	Not an objective per se. Assumption that value created will benefit all parts of society	Specific inclusion policies	Universal social policies

5.2.2.2. QUALITATIVE ATTRIBUTE TABLES

When designing a storyline for a policy-action scenario, the main elements to take into account are the policy objectives and measures. A number of policy measures may be consistent with each storyline (of course, one same policy measure or target can be part of different storylines). For this step, qualitative attribute tables are a useful tool. These tables represent properties that describe the development of key storyline features. They are used to guide quantification and modelling; hence they refer to exogenous inputs (hypothesis, policy targets, behavioural change, and policy measures). As a starting point, current trends are taken as reference to build a baseline scenario. It is varying these trends to above or below current trends when we get exogenous variations on current trends and, therefore, a policy-action scenario.

A good example of a qualitative attribute table can be found in Table 2. In this case, the reference narratives are the SSPs, and for each of them, different assumptions regarding demographic and human elements the exogenous variations are characterized, expressing them mostly as Low, Medium and High or with more detail. Asking questions can shape the guiding lines that can be followed to create the qualitative attribute table (for example: What should the scenarios achieve? What subjects should they cover? What is their time horizon?). We have also created a template of a qualitative attribute table which can be used to create and compare storylines (Table 3). The template can be found in Table 2, as well as in the documentation folder aforementioned.

Table 2. Summary of assumptions regarding demographic and human elements of SSPs. Country groupings referred to in table entries for human development are based on the World Bank definition of low-income (LIC), medium-income (MIC) and high-income (HIC) countries. Source: O’Neill et al., 2017

SSP element	SSP1			SSP2			SSP3			SSP4			SSP5		
	<i>Country fertility groupings for demographic elements</i>														
	High fert.	Low fert.	Rich-OECD	High fert.	Low fert.	Rich-OECD	High fert.	Low fert.	Rich-OECD	High fert.	Low fert.	Rich-OECD	High fert.	Low fert.	Rich-OECD
Demographics															
<i>Population</i>															
Growth	Relatively low			Medium			High			Low			Relatively high		
Fertility	Low	Low	Med	Medium			High	High	Low	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	High
Mortality	Low			Medium			High			High	Med	Med			
Migration	Medium			Medium						Medium			High		
<i>Urbanization</i>															
Level	High			Medium			Low			High	High	Med	High		
Type	Well managed			Continuation of historical patterns			Poorly managed			Mixed across and within cities			Better mgmt. over time, some sprawl		
Human development															
Education	High			Medium			Low			V.low/uneq.	Low/uneq.	Med/uneq.	High		
Health investments	High			Medium			Low			Unequal within regions, lower in LICs, medium in HICs			High		
Access to health facilities, water, sanitation	High			Medium			Low			Unequal within regions, lower in LICs, medium in HICs			High		
Gender equality	High			Medium			Low			Unequal within regions, lower in LICs, medium in HICs			High		
Equity	High			Medium			Low			Medium			High		
Social cohesion	High			Medium			Low			Low, stratified			High		
Societal participation	High			Medium			Low			Low			High		

Table 3. Template of the Qualitative Attribute Table for WILIAM. Source: Own elaboration.

Module	Attribute	Level	Sources	Comments
DEMOGRAPHY	Fertility rates			
	Urbanization			
	Mortality			
	Migrations			
	Migrations due to climate change			
	Population growth			
SOCIETY	Gender parity			
	International cooperation & Global governance			
	Environmental awareness			
	Socioeconomic inequality			
ECONOMY	Carbon taxing			
	International trade			
	Real GDP growth			
	Real GDP per capita Growth			
	Carbon price			
	Unemployment rate			
	Private-public collaboration			
	Provision of public basic services			
	Public debt payment priority			
	Technological development?			
	Climate change economic impacts			
	Inequality between countries			
MATERIALS	Waste recycling			
	Minerals recycling			
	Availability of coal			
	Availability of oil			
	Extraction of fossil fuels resources related to total availability			
	Extraction of mineral resources related to total availability			
	Availability of gas			
ENERGY	Renewable energy generation			
	Energy efficiency			

	Decarbonization of energy sector			
	Nuclear energy production			
	Energy consumption of transport			
	Biofuels presence in the energy mix			
	Green hydrogen presence in industry			
	Green hydrogen presence in energy sector			
	Production of energy with CCS systems			
	Energy consumption of buildings			
	Energy consumption of economic sectors			
	Electrification of energy demand for transport			
	Electrification of energy demand for economic sectors			
	Electrification of energy demand for buildings			
	LAND AND WATER	Afforestation and reforestation		
Presence of plant-based diets				
Protection of Natural ecosystems				
Agricultural soil protection				
Land for renewable energies				
Protection of primary forest				
Carbon capture and storage agroecological practices presence				
Agricultural productivity				
International trade of agricultural products				
Agricultural protection policies				
Land under IUCN categories protection				
Contamination of blue water sources				
Water stress				
CLIMATE	Emissions			
	Temperature rise			
	Salinity of ocean			
	Acidification of ocean			
	Presence of extreme weather phenomena			
	Activation of tipping points			

It is helpful to have in mind here the hierarchy that exists among goals, policy objectives, policy targets and policy measures, which is shown in Figure 4. The size of each box is related to the possible number of options available. This means that: more measures can be associated to one target, more targets to one objective and more objectives to a single goal. There exists a many-to-many relationship among the different boxes.

5.2.3. PARAMETRIZATION OF SCENARIOS

After qualitatively describing the scenarios, a quantification of exogenous parameters to reproduce a given policy or hypothesis consistent with a given storyline is needed. This is what is called parametrization. This is different of the structure, which refers to the equations and logic relationships between exogenous parameters and model variables that represent the implementation of a policy/hypothesis.

Figure 4. Schematic example of the hierarchy of the policy concepts. Source: (Luzzati, T et al., 2021)

Once the qualitative attribute table is created, its parametrization of scenarios is done through the excel file scenario_parameters.xlsx (Figure 5). In the case of WILIAM, the qualitative tags Low, Medium and High can be used to be quantified for each dimension and region. This means filling the qualitative attribute table replacing the qualitative information by numbers. Then, the model user can also identify some additional goals just to check if the resulting adaptive scenario also fulfils them.

The parametrization of a policy usually involves several parameters (e.g., initial implementation year, target year, target value, speed of implementation, etc.). Before parametrizing, it is indispensable to understand how each policy is modelled; if the documentation available is not sufficient, you should try to reach the responsible modeller through Module or Scenarios and Policies coordinators, and ensure clarifications are included in further releases of the model.

In the scenario_parameters.xlsx file, there is a by-default parametrization of the scenario inputs. It is important to highlight that this parametrization refers just to an initialization of the model and should not be considered a consistent baseline or reference scenario.

#	Policy or Hypothesis Name	Policy or Hypothesis Name In Wiliam Model	Module Name	Submodule Name (Wiliam View in Vensim)	Brief Description
POLICIES (measures and targets)					
P1	Fertility rates	FERTILITY_RATES_SP	Demography	demography-population_change	This policy target defines the fertility rates for the future in regions by 2050. Values are based on the historical period (2005-2020). To parametrize this policy, the user can choose between: low fertility rates (1), average (2) or high (3). The data for the different options (low, average and high) is available at the sheet "demography_data".
P2	Life expectancy at birth	LIFE_EXPECTANCY_AT_BIRTH_SP	Demography	demography-population_change	This policy target defines the life expectancy at birth for the future in regions. Values are based on the historical period (2005-2020). SELECTION: minimum Life Expectancy at Birth (1), average (2), or maximum (3). There is also an option to activate or deactivate the SWITCH (SWITCH DEM LIFE EXPECTANCY AT BIRTH) to choose between (0) exogenous pathway and (1) endogenous feedbacks for life expectancy at birth.
P3	Migrations	MIGRATION_SP	Demography	demography-population_change	This policy target activates (1) or disactivates (0) the existence of international bilateral migration flows for the future. Default included data from (Abel&Cohen, 2022): https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01271-z , but they can be changed
P4	Evolution of EU27 households composition	SELECT_SLOPE_EVOLUTION_OF_EU27_HOUSEHOLDS_COMPOSITION_SP	Demography	demography-households_composition	Value for the switch scenario for households composition for EU27 countries. 4 options for the evolution of the ratio of households per 100 people over time available from the statistical analysis of past data: 0 (Constant 2015 values), 1 (Mean values for future trend), 2 (Maximum Ruralization values for future trend), 3 (Maximum Urbanization values for future trend)
P5	Evolution of number of people per household in non-EU regions	VARIATION_OF_AVERAGE_PEOPLE_PER_HOUSEHOLD_IN_NON_EU_REGIONS_SP	Demography	demography-households_composition	Variation over time of average number of people per household for non EU regions.
P6	Speed of the evolution of households	BUFFER_HOUSEHOLDS_SPEED_OF_CHANGE_SP	Demography	demography-households_composition	Parameter to modify the speed of the scenario assumption of the evolution of households composition. Three options: (1) slower speed than historical years; (2) similar speed than history; (3) faster speed than the historical change in household composition.
P7	Gender parity in education	GENDER_PARITY_INDEX_TARGET	Society	society-education	Socio-economic index designed to calculate the relative access of men and women to education. This index is released by UNESCO. In its simplest form, it is calculated as the quotient of the number of females by the number of males enrolled in a given stage of education (primary, secondary, etc.). A GPI =1 means equality between males and females. A GPI <1 is an indication that gender parity favors males while a GPI >1 indicates gender parity that favors females. The closer a GPI is to 1, the closer a country is to achieving equality of access between males and females. This is a policy target in WILIAM to be set for a final year per region.
P8	Capital productivity change	CAPITAL_PRODUCTIVITY_VARIATION	Economy	economy-firms_investment	Annual change in capital productivity by sector and country. Capital productivity is measured as the ratio between real output and real capital stock.
P9	Producers' mark-up	MARK_UP	Economy	economy-prices	Policy to establish the producers' mark-up, which refers to the share of profits over total price. The user defined values can be modified in terms of region and sector.
P10	Labour productivity change	LABOUR_PRODUCTIVITY_VARIATION	Economy	economy-labour	Annual change in labour productivity by sector and region. Capital productivity is measured as the ratio between real output and number of hours worked. When positive numbers are introduced, the annual change in labour productivity increases, and it decreases when introducing negative numbers.
P11	Working time variation	WORKING_TIME_VARIATION_SP	Economy	economy-labour	This policy introduces Introduce cumulative working time variation (% change) between final and initial year (positive number increases, negative number decreases). After the final year the number of hours remain constant. It is recommended to combine this policy with changes in labour productivity (i.e., combine a reduction in working time with an increase in labour productivity). Working time is measured as annual hours per worker by sector.
P12	Debt interest rate	DEBT_INTEREST_RATE_SP	Economy	economy-government finance-households	This policy refers to the interest paid by governments for their debt. This interest rate also affects the interest rates paid or received by households for their financial liabilities/assets.
P13	Government deficit of surplus	GOVERNMENT_BUDGET_BALANCE_TO_GDP_OBJECTIVE_TARGET_SP	Economy	economy-government	This policy establishes the government deficit of surplus related to a GDP target. For countries that in 2015 show a balance/GDP ratio > -3%, it is assumed a linear reduction to -1.5% by 2050, and from 2050 to 2100 a reduction to -1%. For countries that in 2015 show a balance/GDP ratio < -3%, it is assumed a 50% reduction until 2050 and from 2050 to 2100 a reduction to -1%.
P13	Limit to the annual growth of government expenditure	LIMIT_ANNUAL_GROWTH_GOVERNMENT_EXPENDITURE_SP	Economy	economy-government	This policy limits the annual % of growth of government expenditure. The user can define this limit, as well as the initial year in which the policy starts.
P14	Income tax rate	TAX_RATE_INCOME_SP	Economy	economy-households	This policy imposes a tax rate on households income, separated by type of household.
	Wealth tax rate	TAX_RATE_WEALTH_SP	Economy	economy-households	Tax rate on households wealth, by type of household. For households, wealth refers to the value of all the

Figure 5. View of the list_policies_hypotheses sheet in the scenario_parameters-xlsx file. Here the user can find a general description of the policies modelled in WILIAM and how to modify the inputs in order to design new scenarios.

The general steps to parametrize a scenario parameter are:

1. Literature review to get information about which policies or targets are being considered in consistency with the narrative that wants to be simulated (official documents, papers, reports, other modelling works which have modelled the same narratives, etc.).
2. Complete/build qualitative input tables by narrative and attribute.
3. Parametrize (quantify) the scenario parameters inputs for each policy and scenario. We can work with deterministic and probabilistic information (for the later, find/estimate an uncertainty input distribution). For this step, there exists a hierarchy in the information collected:
 - a. If there is an official plan or strategy aligned (i.e., European Green Deal, Nationally Determined Contributions, National Climate Change and Energy Plans, etc.) with the narrative you want to simulate for a given policy, prioritize it.
 - b. If no such official plan exists, review the literature to see what is proposed. If there is convergence/alignment between the different proposals, a mean or median can be taken, and if there is divergence/discrepancy this would be the starting point to justify applying different 'scenario cases' or uncertainty scenarios.
 - c. If there is no reference in the literature or they are too vague to parameterize, then the researcher applying the model needs to do a justified expert-judgement.
4. Data management and documentation: it is necessary that the parametrization of scenarios is well documented, since normally it will involve several researchers in a model like WILIAM. We have developed a cooperative workflow in order to structure the parametrization and make it more transparent. To do this, 8 documents need to be created, 1 describing the narrative and 7 .xlsx files (1 per module) which include qualitative attribute tables, goals of the storyline and the information to define the scenario inputs, with detailed explanations on how to use the excel file in the 'ReadMe' tab.

The main steps for the parametrization are the following:

- a. Select a version of WILIAM where to implement the model
- b. Fill in of qualitative attribute tables and storyline overall goals related to each module (Figure 6)

MODULE	ATTRIBUTE	LEVEL	SOURCES	COMMENTS
LAND AND WATER	Afforestation and reforestation	HIGH	https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/kcbd/actions-tracker/	Target 9 - Three billion additional trees are planted in the EU, in full respect of ecological principles.
	Presence of plant-based diets	MEDIUM	https://knowledge-gateway/food-based-dietary-guidelines-europe-table-18_en	
	Protection of Natural ecosystems	HIGH	https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/kcbd/actions-tracker/	Target 1 - Legally protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's land area and a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area, and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network.
	Agricultural soil protection	HIGH	Estrategia de la UE para la Protección del Suelo para 2030 https://energy	

Figure 6. Example of qualitative attribute table for the Land and Water module.

- c. Literature review to collect qualitative and quantitative information about trends, targets, policy measures and instruments, etc. of each scenario input parameter.
- d. Synthesis about how to use literature review to parametrize the scenario inputs (Figure 7).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I																																																																									
1	Person in charge	Daniel																																																																															
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4	Escala temporal	Target:	Text:	Source:	<table border="1"> <caption>Table 15 The total area of industrial forest plantations required under each scenario</caption> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Country or region</th> <th rowspan="2">Current area (1995)</th> <th colspan="3">Projected area in 2050 required under each scenario (in million ha)</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Scenario 1</th> <th>Scenario 2</th> <th>Scenario 3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>North and Central America</td> <td>18.9</td> <td>18.9</td> <td>29.3</td> <td>43.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>United States</td> <td>18.4</td> <td>18.4</td> <td>29.5</td> <td>41.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>South America</td> <td>5.4</td> <td>5.4</td> <td>8.4</td> <td>13.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Asia</td> <td>41.8</td> <td>41.8</td> <td>64.8</td> <td>119.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>China</td> <td>17.5</td> <td>17.5</td> <td>27.1</td> <td>69.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>India</td> <td>4.1</td> <td>4.1</td> <td>8.4</td> <td>17.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Japan</td> <td>10.7</td> <td>10.7</td> <td>16.6</td> <td>12.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Oceania</td> <td>2.7</td> <td>2.7</td> <td>4.2</td> <td>5.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Africa</td> <td>3.6</td> <td>3.6</td> <td>6.6</td> <td>8.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Europe</td> <td>8.7</td> <td>8.7</td> <td>13.5</td> <td>15.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Countries of the former USSR</td> <td>22.2</td> <td>22.2</td> <td>34.4</td> <td>38.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Russian Federation</td> <td>17.1</td> <td>17.1</td> <td>26.5</td> <td>21.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>193.3</td> <td>193.3</td> <td>199.2</td> <td>234.2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Country or region	Current area (1995)	Projected area in 2050 required under each scenario (in million ha)			Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	North and Central America	18.9	18.9	29.3	43.2	United States	18.4	18.4	29.5	41.2	South America	5.4	5.4	8.4	13.6	Asia	41.8	41.8	64.8	119.5	China	17.5	17.5	27.1	69.3	India	4.1	4.1	8.4	17.7	Japan	10.7	10.7	16.6	12.4	Oceania	2.7	2.7	4.2	5.7	Africa	3.6	3.6	6.6	8.9	Europe	8.7	8.7	13.5	15.3	Countries of the former USSR	22.2	22.2	34.4	38.0	Russian Federation	17.1	17.1	26.5	21.7	Total	193.3	193.3	199.2	234.2
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Total	193.3	193.3	199.2	234.2																																																																													
5	2000-2050	Increasing 75%	Potential production in European industrial forest plantations is expected to increase by 75 percent. On average, Scenario 2 requires a 55% increase in the area of industrial forest plantations, but expansion is unlikely to be uniform across countries	https://www.fao.org/4/x8423e/x8423E14.htm																																																																													
6	2000-2051	Increasing 55%		https://www.fao.org/4/x8423e/x8423E14.htm																																																																													

Figure 7. Literature review for the parameter FOREST_PLANTATIONS_INCREASE_SP.

- e. Parametrization. Fill of tables as they are in scenario_parameters.xlsx**
- f. Results analysis. 3 dimensions: (1) validate the implementation of the policy (direct impact in the model is correct), (2) describe the chain of influences from the immediate variables to the overall goals, and (3) identify possible synergies/trade-offs with other policies.

For specifications and more detailed information, see Appendix I.

Also, it is recommendable to cross-check with responsible modellers of the policies in case of doubts.

In order to fill the scenario_parameters.xlsx check the aforementioned [WILIAM User Guide](#).

Finally, it is important to highlight that the final scenario is the adaptive scenario. We assume over some exogenous variables, but the model complements it with results on the endogenous variables. In turn, we cannot know a priori what the quantitative trends are on some variables. We can make pre-assumptions following common sense but not specific trends, and some of our pre-assumptions can be debunked by obtaining counterintuitive results in some cases because we cannot realise some feedback loops. In this sense, the use of the model also helps to check the feasibility of a storyline.

6. SOME IDEAS FOR HELPING TO INTERPRET WILIAM RESULTS

Interpreting the results of large and complex models such as WILIAM is not always easy, obvious nor straightforward. Due to the existence of many feedback loops and of the properties of complex models such as emerging properties and surprise behaviour (REF), the results may be difficult to interpret and even in some cases seem counter-intuitive even for developers. Here we provide with some basic ideas to help in this task.

A pre-condition to correctly interpret WILIAM results is to study in detail its documentation to interiorize which factors are represented (and which not), and how. Users should ask themselves: what are the basic relationships between the different modules?; which ones are the key inter-module variables?, etc.

This formal documentation needs to be completed by familiarization with the utilization of the model, through many test runs allowing to get practical and direct feedback through observing real results. The basic idea is to understand the basic mechanics of the model and modules in different situations (starting by the by-

default simulation of the Baseline). Different methods can be used to interpret the WILIAM results in a systematic way:

1. Running ad hoc tests
2. Extreme conditions tests
3. Modularization and switches (through /scenario_parameters/switches.xlsx)
4. Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis
5. Loop dominance analysis
6. Usage of results' templates/interfaces

Running ad hoc tests represent an exploration of the results of the model and is a flexible method in order to “get a sense” of how the model is built and what are the type of results obtained. It is recommended to start modifying exogenous parameters from the scenario_parameters.xlsx file, although changes in the code can also be done for full flexibility. A particular case are extreme conditions tests.

SWITCHES in WILIAM refer to binary parameters which can hence take just two values (0/1) and which mean connect/disconnect (i.e., ON/OFF) a module, submodule, feature, link, feedback, etc. They are programmed in a way that they allow to easily deactivate (SWITCH=0) particular features, links, feedbacks, etc. for both testing purposes as well as easing analysis of results. By comparing results with SWITCHES set to ON (=1), it is possible to assess the differences of introducing a given feedback or link.

Sensitivity analysis is the study of how variations in parameters or input variables can affect the output of a mathematical model (cf. (Markovska et al., 2023) Annex A2). The variation in the input variables can be due to uncertainty sources or to being the object of controllable decisions. It is closely related to uncertainty analysis, which focuses on the quantification and propagation of uncertainty. The analysis of the sensitivity of a mathematical model, in general terms, can be useful in many steps of modelling and analysing results, since it allows to:

- Test the robustness of the model results with the presence of parametric uncertainty.
- Better understanding of the relationships between the input and output variables of the model.
- It is a way to find errors in the model, for example when unexpected relationships between inputs and outputs appear.
- It is a key aspect for the correct interpretation of the model results and consequently for policy makers.
- It facilitates the choice of input variables that are the object of decisions. Those input variables with maximum sensitivity over the output variables can be the object of optimal decisions.

Different methods can be used, such as Monte Carlo or varying one-factor-at-a-time, the latter typically testing the effects of connecting/disconnecting one feature, link, feedback, submodule or even full module, as aforementioned.

All the above methods are extensively used at GEEDS. There is one last method with great potential which has not been to date applied in the group: loop dominance analysis (Schoenberg et al., 2020); a feature which is e.g., implemented in Stella.

Lastly, the utilization of results templates/interfaces is a technical element which facilitates enormously the interpretation of results. Vensim produces results in each simulation for thousands of variables which are dispersed through the full model and many times have many subscripts (e.g., 62 sectors, 35 regions, 42 PROTRAs, etc.). Despite the creation of indicators' views in the .mdl tries to mitigate this issue, the excel templates of results allow visualize several variables simultaneously with a sensible aggregation. The use of

this tools is hence a very efficient way of working. In the /ToDo&Documentation/ folder there is at the moment 1 template for the energy module. Another similar option would be the usage of Venapps feature in Vensim to embed the figures in the .mdl.

Due to the current immaturity of WILIAM, it is very likely that its users will find some results which cannot interpret, or which can even suspect they may be errors. In these cases, it is very important that you get in contact with the main developers following the guidelines in the [WIKI GITHUB](#) (cf. section ERROR & QUERY REPORTING).

7. IDEAS TO LINK WILIAM WITH A LOCAL MODEL

As it has been mentioned before, this is a general guide and each research has its specificities. Despite that, there may be different motivations to link a higher resolution model, such as WILIAM, with other lower geographical resolution models. WILIAM is a multi-regional model whose lower resolution corresponds to the country level, which poses a problem when analysing regional or local issues. On the other hand, these regional and local issues are also affected by country and global contexts. In these cases, two general solutions are possible depending on the outputs generated by the so-called “parent-model” (in this case, WILIAM) and the so-called “child model”, which refers to the lower geographical resolution model (see Figure 8):

1. “Direct” soft-linking: when the output of the parent model corresponds with an input of the child-model. In these cases, the process is quite simple and consists of:
 - a. Simulating a scenario with the parent model. In this step it is very important to define the chosen scenario in consistency with the scenario developed for the lower-resolution model.
 - b. Export the values over time for the outputs, which will be the inputs for the child model.
 - c. Import the timeseries as inputs to the child model.
2. Soft-linking through a downscaling process: when the output of the parent model is at a too large geographical scale to be directly plugged-in into the child model. In these cases, one more step is added with relation to the soft-linking:
 - a. Simulating a scenario with the parent model. In this step it is very important to define the chosen scenario in consistency with the scenario developed for the lower-resolution model.
 - b. Export the values over time for the outputs which will be the inputs for the child model.
 - c. Downscale these results to the needed geographical scale.
 - d. Import the downscaled timeseries as inputs to the child model.

Figure 8. Representation of two general ways of soft-linking 2 models with different geographical resolution. In italics is given one example for each.

The MEDEAS models are an **example** of the use of “direct” soft-linking between their different dimensions, as it can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Example of one-way integration of different geographical scale models in MEDEAS framework. MEDEAS-W is the parent model of MEDEAS-EU, while the MEDEAS-country levels models have 2 parent models: both W and EU. The direction of the arrows represents outputs from the parent models which feed the child models (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2020)

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10. APPENDIX I

1. GUIDELINES FOR THE DOCUMENTATION OF THE PARAMETRIZATION PROCESS OF A SCENARIO IN WILIAM

The parametrization of a model of the size and the complexity of WILIAM requires a structured and transparent way of treating and storing information. Very often this parametrization work will involve several researchers in different modules. Then, it is necessary that the workflow includes the possibility of collaborative work in shared documents. If the parametrization is to be performed by just one person, the workflow described below could be simplified.

To reach these goals of structuring, transparency and cooperation, the following workflow has been developed. Note that these guidelines are necessary flexible and each team facing the task of parametrizing a scenario with WILIAM can and should adapt them to their specific needs. Also, the experience will contribute to improving these guidelines, which are a live process.

1.1. GENERAL WORKFLOW

The **general idea** is to create 8* documents shared online will be created:

- 1 .docx describing the narrative, including the pursued goals
- 7* excels (1 per module to ease collaborative work and avoid having too large excels) including the attribute qualitative tables, goals and the information used to define all the scenario inputs present in scenario_parameters.xlsx following the developed template (**template_documentation_scenario_inputs_scenarioX_moduleY.xlsx**, available as Supplementary Material). Detailed explanations on how to use the excel are provided in the 'ReadMe' tab of the template. The main steps are:
 1. Select a version of WILIAM where to implement the model and indicate it in the template, copying the number of the used commit (i.e.: 55445a8f639b83e4ceb50efaa35ba696527471fa).
 2. Define the simulation time horizon, meaning, the target year of the scenario. This is different from the target year of scenario inputs, which refers to the final year of specific policies to be fully implemented. The information of the steps 1. and 2. will be compiled in the tab "general_info".

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Module	name_of_module				
2						
3	Person in charge	Manolo				
4						
5	WILIAM version + commit	WILIAM_version_commit				
6						
7	Final year simulation	final_year				
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						
13						
14						
15						
16						
17						
18						
19						
20						
21						
22						
23						
24						
25						

Figure 3. general_info tab.

3. Fill in of qualitative attribute tables and storyline goals related to each module

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Person in charge	Manolo						
2								
3	1. QUALITATIVE ATTRIBUTE TABLE							
4	present in the narratives in the literature, which are also complemented with the storyline goals; this step is useful to later create policy measures that are consistent with the storyline.							
5	WILIAM modules are the chosen categories to characterize.							
6	The attributes have been selected combining relevant literature and WILIAM characteristics. Some attributes can be not represented in WILIAM, an this is							
7	MODULE	ATTRIBUTE	LEVEL	SOURCES	COMMENTS			
8	DEMOGRAPHY	Fertility rates						
9		Urbanization						
10		Mortality						
11		Migrations						
12		Migrations due to climate change						
13		Population growth						
14	SOCIETY	Gender parity						
15		International cooperation & Global governance						
16		Environmental awareness						
17		Socioeconomic inequality						

Figure 4. Example of the Qualitative attribute table in WILIAM.

- Literature review to collect qualitative and quantitative information about trends, targets, policy measures and instruments, etc. of each scenario input parameter.

A	B	C	D
Person in charge		Daniel	
1. LITERATURE REVIEW			
1. Literature review to collect qualitative and quantitative information about trends, targets, policy measures and instruments, etc. of each scenario input parameter			
Escala Temporal	Target:	Text:	Source:
2030-2030	3 Billion Tree Planting Pledge for 2030.	Target 9 - Three billion additional trees are planted in the EU, in full respect of ecological principles. La Estrategia de la UE sobre la Biodiversidad de aquí a 2030 establece el compromiso de plantar, al menos, 3 000 millones de árboles adicionales de aquí a 2030, con pleno respeto de los principios ecológicos . Esta iniciativa actuará contra la tendencia actual de aumento neto decreciente de la superficie forestal de la UE. Con el tiempo, también contribuirá a aumentar la cubierta forestal de la UE y, con ello, el sumidero y las reservas de carbono de la UE. The majority of European forests are privately owned (approximately 60% of forested land) rather than public (40%) (EU Factsheet). Therefore, afforestation and reforestation practices often involve private landholders, and for being successful, they need to be accepted by these stakeholders by overcoming institutional factors, such as rights and access to forests. represents the main source of EU funds for forests (some 90% of EU funding for forests comes from the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, EAFRD), thus including afforestation and	https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/kcbd/actions-tracker/ https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/afforestation-and-reforestation-as-adaptation-opportunity

Figure 5. Example of the literature review to parametrize land and water policies.

- Synthesis about how to use literature review to parametrize the scenario inputs.

2. SYNTHESIS LITERATURE REVIEW FOR PARAMETRIZATION						
2. Synthesis about how to use literature review to parametrize the scenario inputs. If different trends in the literature are detected, identify different options which can be the basis for uncertainty analysis or different scenario cases. Use this excel to directly report any estimations/calculations done with the available data, figures, etc. to assure the transparency of the parametrization.						
Escala temporal	Target	Area 2015 (ha)	densidad de arboles media en europa (ha)	Area de arboles proyectada	proporcion en relacion a Area 2015	porcentaje
Actualidad-2030	3 Billion Tree Planting Pledge for 2030. 3000000000	1.05882 M km2 1058820000 10588200	1000 árboles por / ha 1000	ha 3000000	DMNL 0,283334278	% 28,33343

Figure 6. Example of the synthesis of the literature review for parametrization of land and water scenario inputs.

- Parametrization. Fill of tables as they are in scenario_parameters.xlsx**
- Results analysis. 3 dimensions: (1) validate the implementation of the policy (direct impact in the model is correct), (2) describe the chain of influences from the immediate variables to the goals, and (3) identify possible synergies/trade-offs with other policies.

The 7* excels will be hard-linked (automatized to minimize human errors) with the scenario_parameters.xlsx of the selected WILIAM version. The idea would be that the cells from the scenario_parameters.xlsx storing the data to be loaded in the model automatically read the data from these 7* excels. This process is to be more efficient than other options assessed as for example: centralization by a coordinator. All the files would be stored in a shared folder in TEAMS. This method has already been successfully tested in order to subsequently run wiliam.mdl reading from it.

3. PARAMETRIZATION

3. Parametrization. Fill of tables as they are in scenario_parameters.xlsx

Below it is just an example of a scenario input. The exact table from scenario_parameters.xlsx needs to be copied in each tab
In case the by-default (aligned with baseline in theory) parametrization of a given scenario input is consistent with the intended storyline to be modeled, then it may not be necessary to hard-link this scenario parameter with the scenario_parameters.xlsx

AFFORESTATION_SP					
POLICY SCENARIO PARAMETERS	SWITCH_AFFORESTATION_SP	YEAR_INITIAL_FOREST_PLANTATIONS_SP	YEAR_FINAL_AFFORESTATION_SP	DMNL	OBJECTIVE_AFFORESTATION_SP
REGIONS_IJ_UNIT	DMNL	YEAR	YEAR	DMNL	
EU27	1	2023	2030	0,28	
UK	0	2015	2030	1,00	
CHINA	0	2015	2030	1,00	
EASOC	0	2015	2030	1,00	
INDIA	0	2015	2030	1,00	
LATAM	0	2015	2030	1,00	
RUSSIA	0	2015	2030	1,00	
USMCA	0	2015	2030	1,00	
ROW	0	2015	2030	1,00	

Policy of increase of managed forest, this is an increase of the high-medium biodiversity forest (not the increase of tree plantations). If SWITCH_AFFORESTATION_SP = 1 the policy is applied starting in YEAR_INITIAL_AFFORESTATION_SP and ending in YEAR_FINAL_AFFORESTATION_SP. This policy competes with the rest of land uses, therefore, the objective area might not be achieved in the final year due to land use changes to other uses.

ReadMe general_info qualitative_attributes+goals scenario_input_i AFFORESTATION_SP FOREST

Figure 7. Example of parametrization of the Afforestation policy within the land use module.

*it may be convenient in some cases to group modules.

**in case the by-default (aligned with baseline in theory) parametrization of a given scenario input is consistent with the intended storyline to be modeled, then it may not be necessary to hard-link this scenario parameter with the scenario_parameters.xlsx.

1.1.1. MAINTENANCE AND UPDATING OF SCENARIO INPUT EXCELS

The process of scenario parametrization is typically long and time-consuming. Given that WILIAM is still a BETA model under development, it may be necessary to adapt the scenario parametrization to a more recent version of the model developed meanwhile. A more recent version of WILIAM may affect scenario parametrization in different ways:

- Model updates may cause changes in how scenario inputs are programmed (eg if they are programmed in relative terms of targets such as % in year 2050)
- All the dynamic links between the excel parametrization excels and scenario_parameters.xlsx will need to be redone (take care here with eventual change in the order of scenario inputs in scenario_parameters.xlsx)
- New scenario inputs created

In this sense, the frequency of updates needs to be assessed carefully.

In case of wishing to perform and update the following steps are foreseen:

1. A version of the model (vDEV-A) is chosen to implement a scenario.
2. A shared folder is created in TEAMS where everyone who will work on the parameterization of that scenario has access. All scenario parameters needs to be assigned to someone.
3. A copy of the scenario_parameters.xlsx of that version of the vDEV-A model is taken to that folder and renamed 'scenario_parameters__DEV-A_scenarioX.xlsx'. In that same folder, the 7* templates are copied (one per module) to parameterize all the scenario parameters. These excels are dynamically linked so that all the number tables of 'scenario_parameters_DEV-A_scenarioX.xlsx' read their content dynamically from the 7 scenario inputs excels per module.
4. Work on parameterization. When this task is finished, the model (vDEV-A) can be simulated with the complete 'parameters_scenarioX.xlsx'. Keep in mind that it could be that in the process we realize that we need to perform changes to the model and/or scenario_parameters.xlsx of WILIAM. 2 clear cases:

if you need to regionalize a scenario input that is not currently regionalized, or if you need to include a new scenario parameter. In this case it would be necessary to make modifications to vDEV_A to have vDEV-A' (assuming a specific branch is opened to work on this scenario in Gitlab).

5. Review process (consistency? are objectives achieved?, etc.) and iteration to improve parameterization

In the meantime, there will be a more updated version of the model (vDEV-B) and therefore also a different scenario_parameters.xlsx. If you want to implement this scenario in the new version of the model, this will require three more steps:

6. analysis of the differences both in the model to understand possible structural changes that affect the parameterization, as well as of the scenario_parameters.xlsx to also detect structure changes and new policies implemented in the meantime (the latter is the "Spreadsheet Compare" tool).
7. it would be necessary to repeat step 3: a person would have to link all the modified scenario inputs with relation to the reference scenario of the new 'scenario_parameters_DEV-B_scenarioX.xlsx' with the 7 existing excels, adapting it to any structural or content changes. The new scenario parameters are assigned to people and need to be parametrized scratch.
8. Steps 4 and 5 above are repeated again.